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Taxation in Dharmaśāstra

Dr. Tarak Jana¹

Abstract

In India, the system of direct taxation as it is known today has been in force in one form or another even from ancient times. Variety of tax measures are referred in both Manusmṛti and Arthaśāstras. The wise sage advised that taxes should be related to the income and expenditure of the subject. He, however, cautioned the king against excessive taxation; a king should neither impose a high rate of tax nor exempt all from tax. According to Manusmṛti, the king should arrange the collection of taxes in such a manner that the taxpayer did not feel the pinch of paying taxes. Kautilya has also described in great detail the system of tax administration in the Mauryan Empire. It is remarkable that the present-day tax system is in many ways similar to the system of taxation in vogue about 2300 years ago. Arthaśāstra mentioned that each tax was specific and there was no scope for arbitrariness. Tax collectors determined the schedule of each payment, and its time, manner and quantity being all pre-determined. Similarly, tolls, road cess, ferry charges and other levies were all fixed.

Keywords

Tax, *kośa*, *Śulka*, *Bali*, Dharmaśāstra

Rājdharma has been the subject of discussion in works of dharmaśāstra from very ancient times. The fulfilment of their duties and responsibilities by rulers was of paramount importance to the stability and orderly development of society and to the happiness of individuals in the state and therefore one often finds that rājdharma is said to be the roof of or the quintessence of all dharmas. According to almost all of our authorities a state (rājya) is constituted by seven

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elements viz. svāmin (ruler or sovereign), amātya (minister), janapada or rāṣṭra (the territory of the state and its people), durga (fortified city or capital), kośa (accumulated wealth in the ruler's treasury), daṇḍa (army), mitra (friends or allies). These seven are called aṅgas. The word 'kośa' is very important in the administration of the state.

Kautilya says that a king whose treasury is depleted preys upon citizens and the rural population and very rightly remarks that all undertakings depend upon kośa (financial position of the king), therefore the king must pay the first attention to kośa.² Gautama holds that kośa is the basis or support of the other six elements of the State. The Sāntiparva calls upon the king to guard his finances with great effort, since kings depend upon kośa, which tends to the prosperity (of the kingdom).³ Kāmandaka states that it is on the lips of all that the king is dependent on kośa. Sānti contains a eulogy of kośa. The Viṣṇudharmottara says there kośa is the root of the tree of State. The two great pillars of the Indian States in ancient India were revenue and the army. Manu says that kośa and the government of the realm depend on the king i. e. they should be the personal concern of the king.⁴ Yājñavalkya recommends that the king should personally look into the income and expenditure every day and keep in his treasury buildings whatever is brought by those who are appointed to bring gold and wealth.⁵ The principal means of filling the treasury is taxation. It is therefore necessary to consider first the principles of taxation as evolved by our writers. The first principle was that the king could not levy, according to the smṛtis, taxes at his pleasure or sweet will that the rates of taxes which the king was entitled to levy were fixed by the smṛtis and varied only according to the commodity and also according as the times were normal or where was danger of invasion or some other calamity impending. For example, Gautam, Manu, Viṣṇu declare that the king may

2 कोशमूलाः कोशपूर्वाः सर्वारम्भाः । तस्मात्पूर्वं कोशमवेक्षेत ॥ अर्थशास्त्र II. 2.

3 कोशश्च सततं रक्ष्यो यत्नमास्थाय राजभिः । कोशमूला हि राजानः कोशो वृद्धिकरो भवेत् ॥ शान्तिपर्व 119. 16

4 अमात्ये दण्डे आयत्ते दण्डे वैनयिकी क्रिया । नृपती कोषराष्ट्रे च दूते सन्धिविपर्ययी ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VII. 65.

5 कृतरक्षः समुत्थाय पश्येदायव्ययी स्वयम् । व्यवहारांस्ततो दृष्ट्वा स्रात्वा भुञ्जीत कामतः ॥ हिरण्यं व्यापृतानीतं भाण्डागारेषु निक्षिपेत् । पश्येत्वारांस्तो दूतान्पेषयेन्मन्त्रिसंगतः ॥ याज्ञवल्क्यस्मृतिः I. 327-328.

ordinarily take a sixth part of the grain-crops or produce of the soil,⁶ but Kautilya, Manu, Śāntiparva, Sukra IV. 2. 9–10 permit the king to take even one-third or one-fourth part of the crops in times of distress (āpad).⁷ It has however to be noted that Kautilya requires the king to beg (yāceta) of the people for this heavy taxation, he employs the word praṇaya (request) for such demands, such taxation was not to be levied from inferior lands, and he expressly says that such a demand for excessive taxation is to be made only once and not twice in the same distress.⁸

Śānti contains a specimen of a long address to be given to the people when a king demands higher taxation in danger. The Udyogparva states 'just as a bee draws honey but at the same time leaves the flowers uninjured, so the king should take wealth from men without harming them. One (a bee) may search each flower (for honey) but should not cut the very root just like a garland-maker, but not like a coal-maker. Manu laconically puts the matter thus 'just as the leech, the calf and the bee take their sustenance little by little, so must the king draw from his kingdom annual taxes little by little.⁹ Let the king not cut up his own root (by levying no taxes) nor the root of others by excessive greed'.¹⁰ Śānti states that the king should draw (taxes) from the realm lightly in the way the bee draws honey from the trees, he should do so in the way of the calf and should not bruise the udders (as the calf does not). Those verses also refer to the action of the leech, of the tigress carrying her cubs between her jaws and the rat gnawing at the feet of sleeping men. These ideas pervaded society so much that the same figure of the bee is mentioned as regards the Buddhist bhikkhu's importance for alms in the Dhammapada (verse 49). The king should act like a gardener who prepares garlands without harming the trees and their leaves and should not act like one who prepares coals from trees.¹¹ Manu says that the king should not through greed tax the

6 गौतम-धर्मसूत्र X. 24, मनुस्मृतिः VII. 130, विष्णु-धर्मसूत्र III. 22-23

7 चतुर्थमाददानोऽपि क्षलियो भागमापदि । प्रजा रक्षन् परं शक्यो किल्विषात् प्रतिमुच्यते ॥ मनुस्मृतिः X. 118.

8 कोशमकोशः प्रत्युत्पन्नार्थकृच्छः संगृह्णीयात् । जनपदं महान्तमल्पप्रमाणं वा द्रवमातृकं प्रभूतधान्यं धान्यस्यांशं तृतीयं चतुर्थं वा याचेत । ... इति कर्षकेषु प्रणयः । ... इति व्यवहारिषु प्रणयः ।...सकृदेव न द्विः प्रयोज्यः ॥ अर्थशास्त्र V. 2.

9 यथाल्पाल्पमदन्त्याद्यं वार्योकोवत्सषट्पदाः । तथाल्पाल्यो ग्रहीतव्यो राष्ट्रद्राज्ञाद्विकः करः ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VII. 129.

10 यथा राजा च कर्ता च स्यातां कर्मणि भागिनौ । संवेक्ष्य तु तथा राज्ञा प्रणेयाः सतत कराः ॥ नोच्छिन्त्यादात्मनो मलं परेषां चापि तुष्ण्या । ईहाद्वाराणि संरुध्य राजा संप्रीतिदर्शनः ॥ शान्तिपर्व 87. 17-18; 47. मनुस्मृतिः VII. 139.;

11 मालाकारोपमो राजन्भव माङ्गारिकोपमः ॥ शान्ति 71.20.

subjects heavily, as he would thereby cut off the roots (i.e., prosperity and contentment) of the people, nor should cut off his own roots by levying no taxes. According to Śāntiparva, a third principle of taxation was that when increasing taxes, the rise should be gradual and a little at a time (शान्तिपर्व 88. 7–8). Taxes were to be recovered at a proper time and proper place.¹² When taxing traders the king should make allowance for the price they had to pay, for the chances of selling the commodity (in his kingdom), the distance over which the merchandise was brought, what they must have spent for their food and condiments and the cost of guarding the merchandise.¹³ In the case of artisans, before taxing them, the king has to pay regard to the labour and skill involved and to the necessities of life required by them. Every one, however poor, must contribute something to the finances of the realm. Manu says that even a very poor man who maintains himself by following some occupation should be asked to contribute every year something in the nature of kara (tax), while workers (like cooks), artisans (like blacksmiths), śūdras who subsist by manual labour (like porters) should be asked to contribute one day's work to the king in a month.¹⁴ Vide Gautama, Viṣṇu Dharmasāstra the same. But Śukra says that workers and artisans should do one day's work for the king gratis in a fortnight. Gautama also says that the king must supply them with food on the day the work gratis. The importance of a gold and silver reserve was well understood.

Kāmandaka says that the king's kośa should have many sources for filling it, but few outlets of expenditure, it should be full of all desired kinds of wealth, guarded by trusty officers, rich in pearls, gold and jewels, it should have been acquired according to śāstric rules, be capable of bearing great strain of expenditure and that kośa is to be preserved only for the purpose of securing the two goals viz. dharma and artha, for affording maintenance to the servants engaged by the king and as a safeguard against calamities.¹⁵ Śukra remarks that kośa

12 आददीत धनं काले त्रिवर्गपरिवृद्धये । यथा गौः पाल्यते काले दुह्यते च तथा प्रजा ॥ कामन्दक V. 83-84.

13 विक्रयं क्रयमध्वानं भक्तं च सपरिच्छदम् । योगक्षेमं च संप्रेक्ष्य वणिजां कारयेत्करान् । शान्तिपर्व 87. 13. मनुस्मृतिः VII. 127 reads भक्तं च सपरिव्ययम् ॥ उत्पत्तिं दानवृत्तिं च शिल्पं संप्रेक्ष्य चासकृत् । शिल्पं प्रति करानेवं शिल्पिनः प्रति कारयेत् ॥ शान्तिपर्व 87. 15.

14 यत्किञ्चिदपि वर्षस्य दापयेत् करसंज्ञितम् । व्यवहारेण जीवन्तं राजा राष्ट्रे पृथग्जनम् ॥ कारुकाञ्च शिल्पिनश्चैव शुद्रांश्चात्मोपजीविनः । एकैकं कारयेत् कर्म मासि मासि महीपतिः । मनुस्मृतिः VII. 137-138.

15 मुक्ताकरनकरत्नाढ्यः पितृपैतामहोचितः । धर्माजितो व्ययसहः कोषः कोषज्ञसमतः ॥ धर्महेतोस्तथार्थाय भृत्यानां

is accumulated for the upkeep of the army and for the benefit of the people and for performing sacrifices. Gautama, Manu, Nārada and others say, as has been already stated, that taxation is meant for the protection of the subjects and that it is the king's wages (vetana) for the protection be afforded. Manu compares the king taking taxes to the sun that produces vapour from the seas. Kāmandaka enumerates eight principal sources of filling the treasury through the action of the heads of the departments viz. agriculture, trade-routes both on land and water, the capital, water embankments, catching of elephants, working mines and collecting gold, leaving wealth, founding towns and villages in uninhabited spots. The Mānasollāsa advises the king to spend ordinarily three-fourths of the yearly revenues and save one fourth. Śukra prescribes that the king should save one sixth of his total annual income and should spend one two of the whole on the army and one-twelfth each on charity, ministers, inferior officials, and his private purse or expenses. The Mānasollāsa says that the king's treasury should be always full of gold, silver, jewels, ornaments and costly clothes, that pure gold in the form of niṣkas or bars or ornaments should be held in the treasury. Kautilya stated above permitted the king in famines to make the rich disgorge their wealth.

Kautilya remarks that if after making special requests for additional taxation, when the treasury is empty and some danger is impending, to the cultivators, merchants, wine-sellers, prostitutes and those who rear pigs, poultry, cattle, the king may request the rich to give as much of their gold as they can and the king may honour them by bestowing on them a post at his court, or the dignity of an umbrella, a turban or some decoration in return for their wealth.¹⁶ He permits the king in calamities to take away the wealth of the corporations (saṅghas) of heretics and of temples also, to set up all of a sudden on one night a god or a platform for a holy tree or a sacred place for a man of miraculous powers and provide for fairs and merry gatherings there and secure the necessary money. He recommends many other tricks and dodges for securing money, which are passed over. Perhaps the only redeeming feature of these devices is that Kautilya is careful to point out that they

भरणाय च । आपदर्थं च संरक्ष्यः कोषः कोषवता सदा ॥ कामन्दक IV, 62-64.

16 सारतो वा हिरण्यमाढ्यान्त्याचेत । यथोपकारं वा स्वक्शा वा यदुपहरेयुः स्थानछत्तवेष्टनविभूपाश्रैषां हिरण्येन प्रयच्छेत् ॥ अर्थशास्त्र V. 2.

were to be employed only against the seditions and the irreligious and not against others. Vide Nītivakyāmṛta for similar provisions to replenish a depleted treasury. Śukra advises the king when in financial difficulties to promise interest to the rich and take their wealth and to return it with interest when the difficulties are over.¹⁷ Śānti asks the king to honour the wealthy men in his kingdom, since they constitute an important element of the realm and are the most eminent among all beings and to request them 'confer along with me favours on the people'.¹⁸ Several reasons are assigned for people's payment of taxes to the king. Gautama X. 28 says that they should do so because he protects them. In some places the idea put forward is that taxes are the wages (vetana) of the king and that the subjects made a contract with the king Manu to that effect.¹⁹ Kātyāyana states that as the king is the owner of the earth but not of other kinds of wealth he is entitled to get the sixth part of the produce of land and that since human beings reside on land, they are declared to be owners (in ordinary parlance, but they have only a qualified ownership).²⁰ Several kinds of taxes are mentioned in the dharmasāstras, arthasāstras and the inscriptions. The oldest word for a tax paid to the king is 'bali'. Ṛgveda speak of the common people as 'balihṛt' (bringers of bali, tribute or tax for the king). In the Taitereya brāhmaṇa says that the people bring bali to him.²¹ In the Aitareya brāhmaṇa the vaiśya is characterized as 'balikṛt' (payer of taxes to another), since brāhmaṇas and kṣatriyas were mostly exempt from taxation. Manu, Matsya, Rāmāyaṇa, Viṣṇu Dharmasāstra employ the word 'bali' in the sense of the sixth part of the produce of land the king levied as tax. Here bali is contrasted with bhāga which is a general term. The word kara appears to mean a tax in general. The word bhāga is also general and means the king's dues on land, trees, drugs, cattle, wealth. The meaning of bhāga is ancient. The Amarakośa treats bali, kara and bhāga as synonymous.

The word śulka generally means the tolls or customs duties levied

- 17 धनिकेभ्यो भूर्ति दत्त्वा स्वापत्तो लद्धं हरेत् । राजा स्वापत्समुत्तीर्णस्तत्वं दधात्सवृद्धिकम् । शुक्र IV.2.11.
 18 धनिनः पूजयेन्नित्यं पानाच्छादनभोजनैः । वक्तव्याश्चनुगृहीध्वं प्रजाः सह मयेति वै ॥ शान्ति 89.29.
 19 Vide शान्तिपर्व 67 and 70. 10, वौधायन-धर्मसूत्र I. 10. 1, नारदस्मृति 18. 48, अर्थशास्त्र 1. 13.
 20 भूस्वामी तु स्मृतो राजा नान्यद्रव्यस्य सर्वदा । तत्फलस्य हि षड्भागं प्राप्नुयान्नान्यथैव तु ॥ भूतानां तन्निवासित्वात्स्वामित्वं तेन कीर्तितम् ॥ कात्यायन ॥
 21 स निरुध्या नहुषो यद्गो अग्निर्विशश्वके बलिहृतः सहोभिः । ऋग्वेद VII.6.5.; अथो त इन्द्रः केवलीर्विशो बलिहृतस्करत् ॥ ऋग्वेद X.173.6. हरन्त्यस्मै विशो वलिम् । तैत्तिरीय ब्राह्मण III. 7.18.3.

from vendors and purchasers on merchandise carried into or out of the kingdom. As examples, indicating thereby that śulka or toll was levied as a source of income (āya) at the toll-gate. The principal and perennial sources of income to the state were three viz. the king's share of the produce of land, tolls and customs duties, fines levied from wrongdoers or defeated litigants. Manu says that the principal tax-payers were agriculturists, traders, manual workers and artisans²² Manu said that the king who, without affording protection, levies bali, kara, śulka, pratibhoga and daṇḍa (fines) goes at once to hell and Vardhamāna explains kara as the dues recovered every month from villagers and city-dwellers (every month or twice a year in Bhādrapada according to Kullūka), śulka as the twelfth share recovered from traders, pratibhoga as the dues in the form of fruits, flowers and vegetables presented every day.²³ A few remarks on these and other taxes must be made here. Manu and several others prescribe that the king is entitled to the sixth, eighth or twelfth part of the yield of grain from land. The tax was to be paid once every year or once in six months according to the custom of the country. The varying rates prescribed by Kauṭilya have been indicated in describing the duties of the sitādhyakṣa. Śukra gives a salutary rule that if a cultivator constructs a tank, a well or an artificial water-course or brings under cultivation land previously fallow, the king should not levy a tax thereon till the person making the expenditure has recovered twice the amount spent by him. Kauṭilya provides that the king may show favour to the cultivators by supplying them with seed, cattle and money and that they should return the advances by easy instalments and that the king shall bestow favours and remissions in such a way that they might tend to swell the treasury and not tend to its depletion.²⁴ It has already been stated that according to the smṛtis the ordinary share of the king was one-sixth, but that in case of the danger of invasion or similar calamity he was allowed to raise it to one-fourth. Megasthenes says that no person is permitted to own land and that besides the land tribute people pay into the royal treasury a fourth part of the produce. This shows that the tax on land was very heavy in the times of Candragupta probably

22 धान्येऽष्टमं विशां शुल्कं विशं कार्षापणावरम् । कर्मोपकरणाः शूद्राः कारवः शिल्पिनस्तथा ॥ मनुस्मृतिः X. 120.

23 योऽरक्षन् वलिमादत्ते करं शुल्कञ्च पार्थिवः । प्रतिभागञ्च दण्डञ्च स सद्यो नरकं व्रजेत् ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VIII. 307.

24 धान्यपशुहिरण्यैश्चैन्नाननुगृहीयात्तान्यनुसुखेन दद्युः । अनुग्रहपरिहारौ चैभ्यः कोशवृद्धिकरौ दद्यात् ॥ अर्थशास्त्र II. 1.

owing to his wars to drive away the Greeks and the huge armies that he had to employ. Manu, Gautama, Mānasollāsa hold that the king is entitled to the fiftieth part of the cattle reared by herdsmen and of the interest earned by those who lend money at interest. This last appears to be analogous to modern income tax. Śukranītisāra makes the tax to be one-thirty-two on the interest earned by money lending.²⁵ Viṣṇu adds cloth to these two. The Manu, Gautama, Mānasollāsa lay down that the king is entitled to a sixth part of trees, meat, honey, clarified butter, perfumes like sandalwood, medicinal plants, rasa, flowers, roots like turmeric, fruits, leaves like palm leaves, vegetables, grass, hides, articles manufactured from bamboo slips, earthenware, articles prepared from stones.

Śulka is of two kinds, what is levied on goods carried by land and what is levied on goods carried by water. Viṣṇu-dharmasūtra state that the śulka is one-twentieth part on merchandise for sale bought and sold in the country itself which is interpreted by some as meaning that five per cent of the price of articles sold should be taken by the king as tax, while the Rājanītiprakāśa explains that the king is entitled only to five per cent of the difference between the cost price and the sale price of merchandise. Manu also is susceptible to these two interpretations, as the commentaries of Medhātithi and Kullūka show.²⁶ The Viṣṇu-dharmasūtra prescribes that the king takes one-tenth on merchandise produced in his own country and one-twentieth on goods imported from a foreign country. Yājñavalkya says that the śulka on goods is twentieth part of the prices of the goods. Kautilya in his chapter on the superintendent of tolls (sulkādhyakṣa) sets out several rules, of which a few interesting ones are given here. Commodities intended for marriage or taken by a bride from her parents to her husband or meant as presents or for the purpose of sacrifices or the accouchement of women or for the worship of gods, or for the ceremonies of caula, upanayana, godāna or for the observance of a vrata or for the consecration of a person for a sacrifice and for other special ceremonies shall be allowed to go free of tolls. Whatever commodities would cause harm to the realm or are useless should be destroyed;

25 वार्धुषिकाञ्च कौसीदाद् द्वात्रिंशंशं हरेन्नृपः । शुक्र. 4.2.128.

26 शुल्कस्थानेषु कुशलाः सर्वपण्यविचक्षणाः । कुर्युरर्घं यथा पण्यं ततो विंशं नृपो हरेत् ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VIII. 398.

whatever is of great benefit and seeds not easily available should be allowed to be imported without charge.²⁷ He further says that śulka is levied on exports and imports of merchandise and that on imports the tax will be one-fifth of the price of the commodities as a general rule and prescribes varying rates one-sixth, one-ten, one-fifteen, one-twenty, one-twenty-five on different kinds of articles. Kautilya gives further rules some of which have been already noted. He prescribes rules for ferries also viz. that brāhmaṇas, ascetics, children, very old people, sick men, messengers, pregnant women are to be provided with free passes by the superintendent enabling them to use the ferries, a man with a load and small animals were to pay one māṣa at a ferry, a cow or a horse two māṣas and so on. The Mānasollāsa prescribes that the king should well guard all harbours or velā-pura that are near the sea, that when the boats of sailors residing in his own country return to the harbour the king should charge one-tenth of the price of goods brought as the duty and that when foreign boats are driven to his harbour by an unfavourable wind, the king should confiscate all their merchandise or may give a little to the owners of those boats. In the connection a very interesting inscription may be referred to. The Motupalli pillar Inscription of the Kākatiya king Gaṇapatideva issues a charter of security (abhaya-śāsana) to the sailors who ply between towns in different countries, islands and continents, 'when ships that made voyages from one country to another were driven or were shattered or touched at a place that was not meant as a place of call, owing to unfavourable winds, former kings forcibly took away all commodities therein such as gold, elephants, horses, but we, considering that wealth is dearer than life itself, have with kindness decided to give everything except the fixed śulka to those sailors who undertake the great venture of crossing the sea, so that thereby we shall secure fame and righteousness, the śulka fixed is as follows'. About śulka to be levied on goods brought by the sea the Baud. Dh. S. (I. 10. 15-16) prescribes that it is ten percent of the cargo except one best article (which is totally exempted). In the Kharepatan grant of the Śilāra king Rattarāja dated śake 930 it is provided that one golden gadyāṇa was levied as duty on each vessel that came from another

27 राष्ट्रपीडाकरं भाण्डमुच्छिन्नादफलं च यत् । महोपकारमुच्छुल्कं कुर्याद्विजं तु दुर्लभम् ॥ अर्थशास्त्र II. 21.

country and one golden dharāṇa had to be paid on each vessel coming from the district of Kandalamūliya excepting Cemulya (modern Cheul) and Candrapura. Śukra lays down some very reasonable rules viz. on the same commodity śulka is to be taken in the same country by the king only once and never more than once; the king may take either 1/16, 1/20 or 1/32 from the vendee or vendor; no śulka is to be taken from the vendor when he has to sell his goods at the same price at which he bought them or for less than the cost price; the king should always take from the buyer the proper śulka after seeing what profit he is going to make. Nārada lays down that whatever is to be used by śrotriyas (brāhmaṇas learned in the Vedas) for domestic purposes is exempt, but not what they may employ in trade; the gifts received by brāhmaṇas, the property of stage players, whatever is carried on a man's shoulders - on all these no śulka must be levied.

Gautama-dharmasūtra, Āpastamba-dharmasūtra and Manu exempt a learned brāhmaṇa, the women of all varṇas, all boys before the signs of puberty appear, all those who stay with a teacher for study, ascetics who are intent on dharma, śūdras that do menial work such as washing the feet of higher varṇas, the blind, the deaf and dumb, the diseased, the cripple, an old man of seventy years or more.²⁸ Though these really required more protection than most people, humanity and higher feelings made them exempt from taxes from very ancient times. The claims to exemption were probably exaggerated and not respected in practice. For example, Nārada states that the king is not to levy tolls or customs duties on articles required by śrotriyas for domestic use but if they engaged in trade, they had to pay taxes on merchandise.²⁹ According to Mitākṣarā on Yājñavalkyasmṛti states that the six exemptions mentioned Gautama-dharmasūtra apply only to a very learned brāhmaṇa and not to all brāhmaṇas. Manusmṛti provides that a king even when he has lost everything should not levy a tax on śrotriyas and relying on this the Vaijayantī explains Viṣṇu-dharmasūtra as referring only to learned brāhmaṇas.³⁰ The Rāmāyaṇa states, differing from other authorities, that the king shares one-fourth of the merit (ascetics) dwelling in his kingdom. There

28 अश्वो जडः पीठसर्पी सप्तत्या स्थविरश्च यः । श्रोत्रियेषूपकुर्वश्च न दाप्याः केनचित् करम् ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VIII. 394.

29 सदा श्रोत्रियवर्ज्यानि शुल्कान्याहुः प्रजानता । गृहोपयोगि यच्चैषां न तु वाणिज्यकर्मणि ॥ नारद VI. 14.

30 त्रियमाणोऽप्यददीत न राजा श्रोत्रियात् करम् । न च क्षुधाऽस्य संसीदेच्छ्रोत्रियो विषये वसन् ॥ मनुस्मृतिः VII. 133.

was corresponding liability on the king, viz. he shared half and half in the demerit due to the sins committed by the subjects' chat are not properly restrained by him.³¹ Manu and Viṣṇudharmottara II. 61. 25 says that he reaps the sixth part of the sin of his subjects.

Kautilya mentions numerous kinds of taxes or dues that were levied by the king. It is not possible to explain many of the terms used by him. In the ancient inscriptions, when making grants of a village and the like, it is usual for the king to specify the exemptions from taxes and dues that weep with the grant. Such exemptions were called pariḥāra, which word occurs in Kautilya and also in the Hāthigumphā Inscription of Khāravēla. The king had numerous other sources of income. Kautilya describes the duties of the superintendent of mines. Everything dug up from mines belonged to the king. According to Manu and Medhātithi thereon the king is entitled to a half of the ore dug out of mines, as he is the lord of the earth and gives protection. In modern times under section ninety of the Bombay Land Revenue Code, the Government has a right to all mines and minerals. Kātyāyana says the king is declared to be the lord of the land, but never of other kinds of wealth, therefore he should secure the sixth part of the fruits of land, a but not otherwise at all. Since human beings reside on land their qualified ownership thereof has been declared. The State itself manufactured salt, took its share in salt manufactured by private persons and levied one sixth as State dues on imported salt. Kautilya mentions ten kinds of revenue from mines. The Mānasollāsa asks the king to guard mines of gems, gold and silver and declares that the Creator made the king the ruler over all wealth and especially over what is inside the earth. Kautilya says that those who sweep the dust (near mines) should get one-third of the valuable things found and the king should get two-thirds and all jewels. The king also had monopolies in certain matters. He alone could catch elephants. Kautilya and Mānasollāsa deal with this matter, the latter describing several methods of catching elephants. Medhātithi and Manusmṛti says that kings have a monopoly as to elephants because it is well known that they are most useful to them and he specifies certain monopolies such as those in saffron, silken cloth and wool, horses, pearls and jewels. Megasthenes states that a

31 यत्करोति परं धर्मं मुनिर्मूलफलाशनः । तत्र राजश्चतुर्भागः प्रजा धर्मेण रक्षतः ॥ रामायण, अरण्य 6.14.

private person was not allowed to keep an elephant or a horse and that those animals were held to be the special property of the king.

The king recovered a sort of road cess through officers called *aniapāla* (guardians of borders or boundaries) viz. one by one-fourth *paṇa* on each cart loaded with merchandise, half a *paṇa* on each head of cattle, one by one-fourth *paṇa* on minor quadrupeds and one *māṣa* on a load carried on a man's shoulders. Śūkra permits for the repairs to the roads a tax on those who use roads. Revenues were raised in numerous other ways such as by charging for stamping weights and measures by fees levied from keepers of gambling halls, from players, singers and musicians, from prostitutes, from forests and pastures. Brhat-Parāśara allows the king in a financial crisis to use even temple funds and make them good when freed from his difficult position. Similarly, it allows the king (in difficulty) to take the wealth of usurers, of low people, of heretics and prostitutes, as the continuance and prosperity temples and the others depend upon the king.³² The Mānasollāsa in its great desire to help the king with the accumulation of wealth advises the king even to resort to alchemy.³³

Kautilya cites at great length the causes that lead to the impoverishment of the subjects, to their being greedy and disaffected. Among these he mentions, 'not paying what ought to be paid and exacting what ought not to be exacted, not punishing the guilty and severely punishing the guilty, not protecting the people against thieves and robbing them of their wealth'.³⁴ He then states that when the subjects become impoverished, they become greedy and when greedy they become disaffected and voluntarily go over to the side of the king's enemy or destroy their own king. In another place Kautilya suggests that a conqueror may employ spies who should encourage the subjects of his enemy suffering from famine, depredations of thieves and wild tribes to tell their king, we shall beg the king for favours but if he does

32 नृपस्य यदि ज्ञातानि देवद्रव्याणि कोशवत् । आदाय रक्ष्य चात्मानं ततस्तत्र च तत् क्षिपेत् । वित्तं वार्धुषिकाणां तु कदर्यस्यापि यद्भवेत् । पाषण्डिगणिकावित्तं हरन्नातो न किल्बिषी । देवब्राह्मणपाषण्डिगणका गणिकादयः । वणिग्वार्धुषिकाः सर्वे स्वस्थे राजनि सुस्थिताः ॥ बृहद्पराशर X. p. 282.

33 धातुवादप्रयोगैश्च विविधैर्वर्धयेद्भनम् । ताम्रेण साधयेत् स्वर्णं रौप्यं बङ्गेन साधयेत् ॥ मानसोल्लास II.4.

34 अप्रदानैश्च देयानामदेयानां च साधनैः । अदण्डनैश्च दण्डयानां दण्डयानां चण्डदण्डनैः ॥ ... अरक्षणैश्च चोरेभ्यः स्वानां च परिमोषणैः 1 ... राज्ञः प्रमादालस्याभ्यां योगक्षेमविधावपि । प्रकृतीनां क्षयो लाभो वैराग्य चोपजायते ॥ क्षीणाः प्रकृतयो लोभं लुब्धा यान्ति विरागताम् । विरक्ता यान्त्यमिलं वा भर्तारं मन्ति वा स्वयम् ॥ कौटिल्य VII. 5.

not agree to bestow favours we shall go to another country.³⁵ Śanti says that if the vaiśyas were neglected. Manu warns who through folly rashly oppress their kingdoms that they may ere long lose their own lives and those of their relatives and also their kingdoms.³⁶ Yājñavalkya is even more emphatic and says that the king who seeks to increase his treasury with wealth extracted by unjust means from the big realm loses his wealth in no time and meets destruction along with his relatives.

Tax collection is a significant issue of the state administration. Various development works of the state are carried out through collection of direct and indirect taxes. Tax is a mandatory liability for every citizen of the country. Taxation in now in India is rooted from the period of Manusmṛti and Arthaśāstra. Present India tax system is based on this ancient tax system which was based on the theory of maximum social welfare.

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36 उपेक्षिता हि नश्येयिर्गोमिनोरण्यवासिनः । तस्मात्तेषु विशेषेण मृदुपूर्वं समाचरेत् । शान्ति. 87.36

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